

DAVLATSHOH SAMARKANDIY'S "TAZKIRAT USH-SHUARO" AND ZAYNIDDIN VASIFI'S "BADOYE UL-VAKOYE" INFORMATION ABOUT NAVOI'S PERSONALITY

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Abstract. *This article deals with information about the life of Navoi in comparison with the works of Davlatshah Samarkandiy, Zayniddin Vosifiy.*

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Bu gulshan ichraki yoqtur baqo guliga sabot,
Ajab saodat erur chiqsa, yaxshilik bila ot.

(Alisher Navoi)

Introduction

Alisher Navoi is a writer who his immortal works raised the literature of his people to the level of world literature and made a great contribution to the treasury of advanced human culture.

Alisher Navoi turned 581 years old - he came to us over the centuries and became our contemporary. There is a secret and a reason for this.

XV century. Movaraunnahr. Terrible civil wars and massacres, unbearable oppression and violence, darkness and depravity. Fraud and looting feudal lords, gossiping kings, beys, officials. Destroyed villages, cities and houses full of sorrow and pain. Hypocritical priests, religion and superstition, injustice and cruelty, lawlessness and poverty.

This is one aspect of the landscape that created and ruled Navoi.

That century again. That country again. People's genius and creativity, wonderful qualities, beautiful dreams and aspirations. Stable peace in certain years. Well-developed craftsmanship and both domestic and foreign trade relations. Great progress in every field of culture. The great people whose names are still mentioned in history are scientists and poets,

composers and painters, architects and calligraphers, their creative methods and works that have enriched the treasury of universal culture. Ulugbek Qazizoda, Rumi and Ali Kushchi, Lutfi and Jami, Mirkhand and Khandamir, Behzod and Muzahhib, Abullays, Abduljamil and Ustad Kulmuhammad are among them.

This is the second side of the landscape that created Navoi - the positive side.

The great poet Alisher Navoi devoted his life to the word and, like a skilled diver, collected beautiful pearls from the ocean of thought, which are still enjoyed by poets and lovers of literature. In the shadow of Navoi's great services, the lexical richness and methodological possibilities of the 15th century Turkish literary language have further increased.

Materials and methods

The first source of information about the life and work of Alisher Navoi is undoubtedly the own works of the great poet. Although Navoi did not specifically write his biography, almost all of the poet's works contain specific ideas about his personality, creative and social activities. In particular, the works of the great poet reflect the social activity of the great poet in the works "Vaqfiya", "Munshoot", his personal life in the works "Majlis un-nafois", "Khamsa", "Munojot", "Khazayn ul-maoniy", "Muhokamat ul-lugatayn ", " Khamsat ul-mutahayyirin ", " Holoti Sayyid Hasan Ardasher "and other works of the poet.

Alisher Navoi's work and personality have always been of great interest. There are even many myths about him. In order to get a clear idea of the personality, attitude and character of a great thinker, it is necessary to carefully read the works of the great thinker and the memoirs of contemporary writers. Information about Alisher Navoi is also given in tazkira, historical and artistic works after the 15th century. In particular, Hasankhoja Nisari's tazkira "Muzakkiri ahbob" is based on Navoi's tazkira "Majlis un-nafois". The total volume of his ghazals is quoted from excerpts

from his poems in Persian. Veteran Herati's *Latoyifnoma* is an important translation of Alisher Navoi's *Majlis un-nafois* into Persian. The 9th session of the work, which was additionally included by the author, is directly dedicated to the life and work of Hazrat Navoi.

Issues related to the life and work of Alisher Navoi, first of all, in the works of the poet, the contemporary of the poet Abdurazzaq Samarkandi's "*Matla'i sadayn va majmai bahrayn*", Mirkhand's "*Ravzat us-safo*", Khandamir's "*Khulasat ul-akhbor*" ", "*Makarim ul-akhlaq*" ", "*Habib us-siyar*" ", "*Badoye ul-Vakoye*" by Zayniddin Vosifiy, "*Tazkirat ush-shuaro*" by Davlatshah Samarkandi, "*Ravzat ul-jinnot*" by Muiniddin Muhammad al-Zamji al-Isfizari, It is found in such historical and tazkira works as Abdurahman Jami's "*Bahoriston*" and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "*Boburnoma*". Below are excerpts from the works of authors who lived at the same time as our great ancestor. They talk about Alisher Navoi's unique qualities and personality.

Results

The first source cited below is *Tazkirat ush-shuaro* by Davlatshah Samarkandi. The concluding part of this work, dedicated to Alisher Navoi, begins with a tribute to Navoi. It is said that his honorable name is the adornment of the preface of the book, the main content of the office of bliss.

The fact that Navoi was a mature man in all respects can be seen only in the poet's description of him as "*Oftobni ta'riflash aql xiraligidan nishona*" speaking about Navoi's father, he said that he was a close person of Sultan Abulqasim Babur, he had a special place among the courtiers, as well as paid special attention to the upbringing of children. The fact that Sultan Abul-Qasim was a patron of talent, a patron of religion and state during the reign of Sultan Hussein Bayqara, the Turkish response of "*Khamsa*", the epic "*Layli and Majnun*" will be discussed separately. The play speaks of several qualities of the sir, in particular, his generosity. It is also noted that

a mosque, a madrasa and a rabots have been built. His words of blessing have been proven through these actions. If we cite Navoi's deeds in this book, it will be a long one, so we will talk about his deeds around Herat, that is the meritorious deeds mentioned in this book are only a part of Navoi's deeds.

Four chapters (14-17) of the collection of memoirs "Badoye 'ul-Vakoye" ("Beautiful events") by Zayniddin Vosifiy are dedicated to the personality of Alisher Navoi. It tells about the character of the sir, his creative dialogue with his contemporaries, various interesting events related to the life of Navoi. Here is a comparative analysis and study of these two great works:

"Tazkirat ush-shuaro"

In this Samarkandiy's work we can find more information about Navoi's father

The concluding part of this work, dedicated to Alisher Navoi, begins with a tribute to Navoi. It is said that his honorable name is the adornment of the preface of the book, the main content of the office of bliss. The fact that Navoi was a man of many facets can be seen in Samarkand's description of the sun as "a sign of insanity."

In this play, the great qualities of Navoi are highlighted. He praised Navoi's father, saying that he was close to Sultan Abul-Qasim Babur, that he had a place among the courtiers, and that he was not indifferent to the upbringing of his children. is said to have matured. Sultan Abulqasim's talent as a protective protector, his patronage of the great Amir's religion and state during the reign of Sultan Hussein, Hamsa's Turkish response, and the epic Layli and Majnun are highlighted. Alisher Navoi's generosity is also mentioned. The fact that under the leadership of Navoi the whole country has been improved, madrassas, mosques and rabats have been built. It is said that his words of blessing were proved by these deeds. It is emphasized that if all the deeds of Navoi are mentioned in this book, it will

be prolonged, and therefore his deeds around Herat will be mentioned, that is, the good deeds mentioned in this book are one of the good deeds done by Navoi.

Badoye ul-Vaqoye

Vosifiy's work is written in a more artistic way

Zayniddin Vosifiy notes: "His Highness Amir Alisher was so skilled in the science of music that if his teacher Abu Nasr al-Farabi were alive, he would wear a student's earring on his ear."

Zayniddin Vosifiy, in his work *Badoye' ul-Vakoye'*, states:

Din ofati ul mug'bachai mohiliqodur, mayxorau bebok,
Kim ishqidin oning vatanim deydi fanodir, sarmastu yaqom chok, –

A composer named Haji Abdullah Marwarid composed a melody for the *Matlali Mustahzod*. At that time, there was no house in Herat where this melody was not played. At one party, the members of the assembly tore their collars as the singer recited this *mustahzad*. " The first composers of Navoi's ghazals were Haji Yusuf Burhan and Haji Abdullah Marwarid. Hundreds of years later, Navoi's songs continue to have a profound effect on modern listeners.

Conclusion

Why are such memoirs written about Alisher Navoi, what is the role and significance of these memoirs in science and student life? Of course, we have no right to forget such great people, because Navoi is a genius of the XV century, a great man, just as each era has its own genius. It is the duty of the next generation to know all that he has done. Sensing this, Navoi's

students, historians, people who saw him and interviewed him wrote such memories about this great figure. The importance and place of such memoirs in modern science is incomparable. Because through such solid evidence, we will be able to study Navoi not only as a poet, but also as a person, as a human being.

In late December 1500, Hussein Boykaro returned from the Astrobod march. According to tradition, all the dignitaries of the palace set out to meet the king. Among them was Hazrat Navoi. Despite his deteriorating health, the poet reached the sultan, who had returned from a journey, and with the help of his companions, laid his head on his chest and fainted. This is described in Makarim ul-Akhlaq: At that moment, by the grace of God, his blessed head became dizzy. His Majesty summoned Hoja Shihabuddin Abdullah to his presence and said, "Do not neglect to take care of me, my situation has changed." At that moment, he dismounted to kiss the nobleman's hand. As the severity of the sudden illness had reached its limit and he was unable to walk, the Emir and Mawlana Jalal al-Din Qasim entered his arms and placed the head of the great Amir in the arms of the high-ranking king. His Holiness was deeply saddened to see the change in the state of the center of greatness and luxury. " The poet is brought home in critical condition. Alisher Navoi, who lay unconscious for three days, died on January 3, 1501, of a stroke.

Confirmation

Thus, ancient written sources and works of folklore testify to Navoi's extraordinary intelligence, wisdom, wit and quick wit even in the circle of friends, contemporaries and comrades. Most importantly, everywhere Navoi is portrayed as a great poet, businessman, statesman, and a visionary thinker.

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